

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: Today, the use of innovative technologies and modern methods in information communication in all fields of science is growing. At present, the widespread use of modern technologies in all disciplines serves to increase the efficiency of the educational process. This article discusses the role of modern methods and technologies in learning English, and details the methods and innovative technologies used to learn English quickly, easily, and effectively.

Keywords: English, modern technologies, interactive methods, innovative technology.

Аннотация: Сегодня использование инновационных технологий и современных методов в информационном общении увеличивается во всех областях науки. На данный момент широкое использование современных технологий по всем предметам служит повышению эффективности учебного процесса. В данной статье рассматривается роль современных методов и

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технологий в изучении английского языка, дается подробная информация о методах и инновационных технологиях, используемых для быстрого, легкого и эффективного изучения английского языка.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, современные технологии, интерактивные методы, инновационные технологии.

As time goes on, people and their needs and wants will change. This is an axiom that does not require proof. We can observe the same historical process in the study of foreign languages, as well as in various aspects of our lives. Thousands of years ago, the need and interest in foreign languages, such as Arabic and Persian, developed in our country, our great scholars organized their research in these languages, and it is clear that our ancient poets and writers created masterpieces in these languages and left an immortal legacy. All this is the need of that time, the demand of that time. So what is the state of language policy today, in the first quarter of the 21st century? What is the impact of global development, new discoveries, especially the Internet, on language learning? Which foreign languages should we pay more attention to in the 21st century, and for what purpose? By the way, the development of the period, the process of globalization requires young people to know several foreign languages. Based on these needs, the Resolution of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" laid the foundation for a new stage in the policy of teaching foreign languages in the country. The main goal of the system of continuing education is to train highly spiritual, competitive and intellectually gifted specialists. Following the implementation of this decision, the process of applying

modern pedagogical technologies in the education system has become widespread. Today, scientific and technological progress requires the introduction of new modern technologies in all areas, including education. Therefore, new models of education are being created, as the "National Training Program" emphasizes the need to provide the educational process with advanced pedagogical technologies. The advantage of teaching a foreign language on the basis of pedagogical technology over previous methods is, firstly, that it considers the educational process as a whole, the purpose of education, its content, methods and means of teaching, design the stages of education, control the educational process and in the design of its project, bringing its components, such as the evaluation of learning outcomes, into an interdependent system. Second, it is not about students memorizing the knowledge they have been given, but about doing practical work at the end of the teaching and learning process.

Pedagogical technology is a teaching tool of the teacher, which, based on the needs of society, effectively forms the social qualities of a predetermined person and sees the system of goal-oriented learning as a system and its components is a technological educational activity that monitors the impact of a particular sequence on students in a particular situation and evaluates the learning outcome. Technology is derived from the Greek word "techne", a skill, art and "logos" - the word, the meaning of which is derived from an ambiguous translation of the English word "an education technology". It should actually be translated as "Educational Technology". The introduction of technology into education has been going on for centuries. Until the late 50s, pedagogical technology was associated

with the creation of a technical environment for traditional education, the construction of a set of automated tools. Today, educational technology is considered as a field of pedagogical sciences. Human psychology plays an important role in the development of technology. Historically, educational technology has operated and evolved tactically. Understands the sum of knowledge about the methods and means of implementing technological processes, as well as the qualitative changes that occur at the facility. Educational technology is a set of concepts that includes:

- Have an idea of the planned results;
- A diagnostic tool to help learners determine their current status;
- A set of training models;
- Criteria for selecting the optimal model for specific conditions. Pedagogical methods do not depend on the tools used. Even the method, which is considered the best technology, if it does not give a positive result, it is not a good way. Conversely, a simple question-and-answer method can significantly increase the effectiveness of education. There are specific aspects of the teaching process in the education system, and the guarantee of effective results is mainly based on pedagogical technologies. In order to shed light on the essence of pedagogical technology, we consider it expedient to dwell on the definitions given by pedagogical didactics.

"Pedagogical technology is a consistent method of creating, implementing and defining all processes of teaching and learning in technical and human factors and through their joint efforts, aimed at accelerating the forms of education"

(UNESCO). "Pedagogical technology is the process by which a teacher (educator) influences students under certain conditions with the help of teaching (educational) tools, and as a product of this activity, the process of intensive formation of pre-defined personality traits in them." "Pedagogical technology - a social phenomenon that intensively forms the pre-determined social qualities that are necessary for society as a result of the systematic influence of the teacher on students in certain conditions with the help of teaching aids." "Pedagogical technology - a factor in managing the pedagogical process PT - the organization of the educational process on the basis of design, features that guarantee its effective results, (pedagogical skills, pedagogical tact, pedagogical style, pedagogical accuracy) innovative features of pedagogical activity (creativity, high professionalism-acmeology, analytical and critical approach-reflection) is a systematic category that fully determines the creation and implementation of new forms and methods of education.

Methodological qualities of pedagogical technology include:

- Technological scheme;
- Scientific basis;
- Systematic;
- Management;
- Efficiency;
- Repetition.

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A new modern approach to the application of new technological processes and new modern methods of teaching in the educational process. The purpose of foreign language teaching is not only to educate students and develop certain, speaking skills, but also to develop students' abilities. development, increasing interest in the foreign language they are learning, using the internal capacity of their memory, and building students' confidence in their own power.

As you know, the educational process is complicated. Foreign language lessons include the stages of developing relevant speaking skills and competencies through the presentation of new learning material, its practice through a variety of exercises, and its application to a variety of speech situations. A number of interactive methods can be used to increase student engagement in the classroom. The term interactive method is derived from the English word "interactive", which means to increase students' internal activity. There are a number of types of this method, some of which are currently widely used interactive methods such as "brainstorming", "business games", "pinboard", "cluster", "sinkveyn", "cubic technology", role-playing games are aimed at increasing the activity of students in the educational process. In interactive teaching, group teaching, small groups of 3-5 people are effective. Summarizing the above, it can be called "innovative technology". Innovative technologies are ways to improve the acquisition of knowledge through the use of factors that increase the effectiveness of education, the design and implementation of various pedagogical processes. Its main purpose is to make innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and students in the educational process, which requires the use of interactive methods. Interactive

methods are based on the active, free and independent thinking of each learner involved in the learning process. When using these methods, learning becomes a fun activity. When using interactive methods, the ability to work independently develops. It is known that today there are more than a hundred types of interactive methods, most of which have been tested and given good results. The main conditions for the introduction of educational technologies in the educational process are:

- The development of free communication of each student in the acquisition of knowledge in the teaching process;
- The main focus in the educational process is to increase the activity of the learner and the use of methods and modern teaching aids that increase the activity in the classroom. Classes conducted on the basis of pedagogical technology nurture the desire of young people to express their views on important life achievements and problems, give them the opportunity to think, to justify their views. Pedagogical technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, in the implementation of which mainly interactive methods are used. In interactive lessons, the teacher directs the activities of students to the purpose of the lesson. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are carried out only through the joint work of teachers and students. The process of such pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, such as ensuring that the student is not indifferent during the lesson, independent thinking, involvement in creativity and research, the continuity of interest in science in the educational process, the teacher and ensures that student collaborations are organized on a regular basis. The main basis of pedagogical technology is the joint

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achievement of the teacher and the student from the set goal to the guaranteed result. Each lesson, topic, subject has its own technology. Pedagogical technology in the learning process is an integrated process in a clear sequence, which is based on the needs and interests of the student, focused on a single goal, carefully designed and guaranteed results.

Pedagogical technology, in general, is based on reproductive (copying) teaching, in which the learning process is focused on mastering the actions of students in typical situations. A distinctive feature of pedagogical technology is that it designs and implements the learning process that ensures the achievement of learning objectives. The technological approach is primarily expressed in a practical instructional structure that allows the implementation of the designed results, rather than a description.

The main way to understand pedagogical technology is to focus on clearly defined goals, to establish regular interactions with the learner, to teach through the learner's behavior, which is the philosophical basis of pedagogical technology. Interaction should form the basis of pedagogical technology and fully cover the learning process.

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